

Effects of Substituents on the Intramolecular Hydrogen Bond in 8-Quinolinol-N-Oxides**

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I. R. spectral and deuteration studies on 8-quinolinol-N-oxides and its 5-nitro-, 5-nitroso-, 5-amino-, 5-phenylazo-, 5, 7-dibromo- and 5, 7-diiodo-derivatives in solid and in solution state confirm the presence of a strong intramolecular unsymmetrical hydrogen bond involving the hydroxyl hydrogen atom and the N-oxide oxygen atom. The structure of the complex absorption pattern in the region 2850 cm^{-1} – 1800 cm^{-1} is explained in terms of Fermi resonance interaction between the ν_{OH} of O–H...O and the overtone and combination bands of $(\delta_{OH} + \nu_{C-O})$ and other fundamental vibrations of the molecule. The absence of any significant absorptions in the ν_{OH} region in the spectra of 5,7-dichloro- and 5,7-dinitro-derivatives coupled with strong and broad absorption in 1500 cm^{-1} – 600 cm^{-1} region is perhaps due to the presence of very short hydrogen bonds in these compounds.

IN recent years there has been considerable discussion of very short (less than $2.5\text{ \AA}$) hydrogen bonds (OH...O) between oxygen atoms¹⁻⁴. Compounds with extremely short H-bonds are of interest since they show unusual spectral features and might include instances of symmetrical H-bonds. During our studies⁵ on "8-quinolinol-N-oxide and some of their metal chelates", we had noticed very complex hydroxyl absorption pattern over a wide range 2850 cm^{-1} – 1850 cm^{-1} in the I.R. spectrum of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide. The series of medium strong bands, on deuteration, shifted and a simplified pattern with three prominent absorptions was observed. It is considered of interest to investigate in detail the origin of this complex absorption and also to study the effect of substituents on the strong intramolecular hydrogen bond present in these N-oxides. Solid and solution I.R. spectra of several 5-substituted and 5,7-di substituted-8-quinolinol-N-oxides and their deuterio analogues have been recorded and the results of our studies are presented in this paper.

Experimental

8-Quinolinol-N-oxide and its 5- and 5,7-disubstituted derivatives were prepared by the reported methods⁶⁻⁹ and were purified by repeated recrystallizations. Their purity was checked by elemental analysis. All the solvents were purified by standard methods. The deuterio analogues were prepared by either refluxing with D_2O (99.8%, Atomic Energy Commission, Bombay) (in the case of 8-HOQNO) or with acetonitrile and D_2O under N_2 atmosphere, followed by evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure. I.R. spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 221 infrared spectrophotometer with

sodium chloride prism grating interchange (spectral slit width 1.5 – 2 cm^{-1} in the region 3000 – 1800 cm^{-1}), using Nujol or hexachlorobutadiene mulls in the solid state or wherever possible, in solvents such as CCl_4 (concentration ranges $\sim 1 \times 10^{-4}\text{ m}$).

Results and Discussion

The spectra of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide in solid as well as in solution show multiple medium strong absorption bands over a wide range 2850 cm^{-1} – 1800 cm^{-1} . In solution spectra the band profiles are unaffected by dilution. These bands are shifted and simplified on deuteration. In 5-nitro, 5-nitroso-, 5-amino-, 5-phenylazo-, 5,7-dibromo- and in 5,7-diiodo-8-quinolinol-N-oxides the absorption pattern is essentially similar. All the spectra of substituted-8-quinolinol-N-oxides except the 5, 7-dichloro- and 5, 7-dinitro-derivatives exhibit definite pattern of absorption in three main regions at ca. 2850 cm^{-1} , ca. 2400 cm^{-1} and at ca. 1800 cm^{-1} . In some cases (5- NO_2 -, 5- NO -, 5- $N=NC_6H_5$ - and 5- NH_2 -derivatives), they have contours rather broad and or weak and in others (5,7-dibromo- and 5,7-diiodo-), they are split into several submaxima (Figs. 3 and 4). However, the absorption (ν_{OH} regions) is irregularly increasing extending to ca. 1800 cm^{-1} . The bands observed in the spectra, in general, at ca. 2800 cm^{-1} moved on deuteration to ca. 2400 cm^{-1} and those at ca. 2400 cm^{-1} moved to ca. 1800 cm^{-1} . The shift of the bands at ca. 1800 cm^{-1} , however, could not be located. One common feature found in the deuterio analogues of these substituted-N-oxides is the partial changes in the shape and intensity of absorption bands at ca. 1600 – 1550 cm^{-1} . The other coupled vibrations, $\delta_{OH} + \nu_{(C-O)}$ and the out of plane deformation mode γ_{OH} also moved on deuteration. The observed absorption features in the region

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Fig. 1. —Infrared spectrum of 5, 7-dichloro-8-quinolinol-N-oxide solid (3700 cm⁻¹ to 600 cm⁻¹)
...The deuterated analogue.

Fig. 2. —Infrared spectrum of 5, 7-dinitro-8-quinolinol-N-oxide solid (3700 cm⁻¹ to 600 cm⁻¹)
...The deuterated analogue.

Fig. 3. —Infrared spectrum of 5-nitro-8-quinolinol-N-oxide solid (3700 cm⁻¹ to 600 cm⁻¹)
...The deuterated analogue.

Fig. 4. —Infrared spectrum of 5, 7-dibromo-8-quinolinol-N-oxide solid (3700 cm^{-1} to 600 cm^{-1})
...The deuterated analogue.

2850 cm^{-1} - 1800 cm^{-1} point to the presence of strong intramolecular unsymmetrical hydrogen bond involving the hydroxyl hydrogen atom and the N-oxide oxygen atom. The hydroxyl stretching absorption ν_{OH} the inplane deformation mode coupled with C-O str.

($\delta_{OH} + \nu_{C-O}$) and the out of plane deformation mode, γ_{OH} observed in the spectra of substituted 8-quinolinol-N-oxides along with OD frequencies are given in Table 1. The ν_{NO} and δ_{NO} frequencies are observed at ca. 1310 - 1280 cm^{-1} and at ca. 820 cm^{-1} - 810 cm^{-1}

TABLE 1—OBSERVED I. R. ABSORPTION BANDS (cm^{-1}) IN THE REGION 2900 cm^{-1} TO 600 cm^{-1} IN 8-QUINOLINOL-N-OXIDES

Compound	ν_{OH}	$\nu_{CO} + \delta_{OH}$	γ_{OH}
8-HOQNO ⁺	*2850 m (2400 m) 2540 m 2400 m (1850 w) 2240 mb 1800 w	1525 s (1295 s) 1270 s (1000 s)	880 m (640 m)
5-NO ₂ , 8HOQNO	2625 m (2300 m) 2350 w,b (1800 w) 1900 w	1530 s (1260 s) 1350 s (1060 m)	800 m (650 m)
5-NO, 8HOQNO	2750 m (2300 m) 2300 m (1850 m) 1800 w	1515 m (1170 s) 1360 s (1050 s)	845 s
5-N=N C ₈ H ₇ , 8HOQNO	2600 vb (2010 w) 1850	1410 m (1260 w) 1310 s (1060 m)	870 m
5-NH ₂ , 8HOQNO	2600 wb 2200 w 2100 w 1900 w	1470 s (1150 m) 1275 s (1010 s)	870 m
5,7-Cl ₂ , 8HOQNO	—	—	1345 s (1010 s)
5,7-Br ₂ , 8HOQNO	2700 b,m (2060 m) 2100 w 1850 w	1470 m (1250 m) 1265 s (1000 s)	830 m (650 m)
5,7-I ₂ , 8HOQNO	2550 vb,w(1960 m) 1900 w	1430 s (1200 m) 1300 s (1000 s)	910 m (680 m)
5,7(NO ₂) ₂ , 8HOQNO	940 m	—	1520 s

⁺8-HOQNO=8-quinolinol-N-oxide.

*The approximate centre of the broad band in the region 2850 cm^{-1} - 1850 cm^{-1} which shifted on deuteration. The values given in the parenthesis are the corresponding OD frequencies.

v=very, m=medium, w=weak, s=strong, b=broad.

respectively in all the spectra of the compounds and there seems to be no change in the position of these absorption frequencies.

The complex absorption pattern observed in the spectra in ν_{OH} region might arise from Fermi Resonance interaction between the hydroxyl stretching band of the strong intramolecular O-H...O hydrogen bond and other fundamental vibrational modes of the molecule and the overtone and combination bands of $(\delta_{OH} + \nu_{C-O})$. The origin of these absorptions is essentially due to anharmonicity. However, there are some other absorptions in this region which cannot be explained on the basis of Fermi Resonance only. The simplified pattern in the deuterio analogues is perhaps due to the less possible number of $(\delta_{OD} + \nu_{C-O})$ and (ν_{OD}) interactions. The profiles of hydrogen stretching I. R. bands of molecules with hydrogen bonds in systems, RAH...BR' are treated by Bratos¹⁰ recently. It is shown that the band shaping mechanisms are the anharmonic coupling between the AH str. and different low frequency external motions and the Fermi Resonance between states involving the AH stretching and some other internal modes.

The electronic characteristics of the substituents in 5-position apparently change electron densities of both hydroxyl and the N-O oxygen resulting in variation of the strength of the H-bond. Similar effects of substituents on intramolecular hydrogen bond have been reported¹¹⁻¹³. The electron withdrawing group in 5-position would make the intramolecular hydrogen bond stronger by decreasing the electron density on the hydroxyl oxygen together with the enhancement of resonance from such as structure II¹¹. Although one would expect the NH₂ group to weaken the hydrogen bond due to its electron donating nature, a contrary effect is observed. When electron releasing groups are at 5-position hydrogen bond also would be strengthened by the increasing in the electron density on the N-O oxygen and by the increased contribution of the structure III.

The I.R. spectra of the 5,7-dinitro- and 5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinol-N-oxides do not exhibit (Figs. 1 and 2) any hydroxyl absorption in the region 2850-1600 cm⁻¹. Strong and broad absorptions at ca.1500 cm⁻¹, 1300 cm⁻¹ and at ca.900 cm⁻¹ are observed which show changes on deuteration. There is no band which could be assigned on the basis of usual criteria to an ν_{OH} vibration in 5,7-dichloro compound. However, the band observed at ca.940 cm⁻¹ in 5,7-dinitro derivative in analogy with previous assignments¹⁴ is ascribed to an ν_{OH} vibration.

Hadzi¹⁵ had characterized two groups of short hydrogen bonds and it has been shown that in the case of the first group the barrier between the two potential minima is small enough to allow proton tunnelling resulting in the split of OH str. bands. In the second group the potential barrier is vanishingly small, the hydrogen bond approaching the symmetrical type. The ν_{OH} frequency becomes small and the characteristic property of the vibration is lost owing to strong vibrational interactions with other modes. Apparently the 5,7-dinitro- and 5,7-dichloro substituted-N-oxides belong to this second group. The O...O distance in 8-quinolinol-N-oxide is 2.48 Å¹⁶ and it might be less in these 5,7-substituted derivatives. Pimentel and McClellan¹ have distinguished three OH...O types in terms of O...O distances and observed that the range R = 2.47 - 2.54 Å is a transition region in which either type of behaviour might be found. For R below 2.47 Å the proton will display centrosymmetric distribution and above 2.54 Å the proton can be expected to be closer to one oxygen atom than the other. It is also pertinent to observe that in 5,7-dinitro- and 5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinol-N-oxides, the nitro or chloro groups in 7-position are increasing the non-linear O-H...O bond strength.

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